

Time Series Metric Extraction for Application Behaviour Modeling

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Abstract

Starting from univariate signals coming from test workloads run under different restriction a consistent single-dimensional signal parametrization method through piecewise-linear functions was defined and packaged in a ready-to-use suite.

The results could be used to characterize the signals and measure their reactions to changes in computing and/or network resources.

More work is still needed for the multidimensional case.

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1 Introduction

1.1 High Luminosity LHC

The High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) project is an ongoing update process to the LHC which aims to increase the number of events in the collider by a factor of 10 to, hopefully, help researchers detect new physical phenomena. The update is estimated to eventually come online in 2026. By then, the expected computing power required by the experiments will increase by a factor of 50-100 using current computing techniques, and the data storage need is expected to be in the Exabyte factor, increasing by a factor of 10, with a required data processing of up to 1 PB/s. [3]

CERN has a fixed incoming budget allotted by its partner countries, and for this reason, it is imperative to research new computing, data analysis, and storage techniques now before the HL update comes in place to allow CERN to perform its operation in a cost-effective way even when the data volumes increase.

1.2 Worldwide LHC Computing Grid

The data and computing power used by the experiments is organized within the LHC Computing Grid, which itself is made up of four tiers:

- **Tier 0:** CERN Data Center in Meyrin, and Wigner Center in Budapest which contribute to the initial acquisition and long-term storage of the data, with the Meyrin site also housing tape records;
- **Tier 1:** 13 sites in big research centers worldwide providing more computing power;
- **Tier 2:** Around 155 smaller sites within research and commercial institutions providing a proportional share of computing power;
- **Tier 3:** End-users.

1.3 Working on a more effective architecture

Starting from resource usage of test runs of the experiments run in the Meyrin Centre, the present work tried to analyze the obtained time series and model them in a simple yet effective way.

The resulting parameters for each series could then be used in a subsequent step to model the computing resource cost of possible changes in the data processing and storage architecture to evaluate their effectiveness.

The work draws from [9] which had similar goals but focused on series extracted by another tool.

2 Available Data

The test runs consisted of the following jobs, categorized by experiment:

- **ALICE**: Simulation task (*sim*);
- **LHCb**: Simulation task;
- **ATLAS**: Derivation task (*deriv*), Digitalization and Reconstruction task (*digireco*), and Simulation task;
- **CMS**: Simulation task (*gensim*), Digitalization task (*digi*) and Reconstruction task (*reco*).

The tasks were run on the same machine, with an 8-core 2.4GHz 32-bit Intel Xeon CPU and up to 16 threads, each time creating a new VM by scratch to avoid contaminations.

Different restrictions were then applied to:

- **RAM**: Restricted from 4 GB to 64 GB (unrestricted case);
- **Latency**: Restricted from 0.1ms (unrestricted case) to 64 ms;
- **Bandwidth**: Restricted from 1mbps to 1250mbps (unrestricted case)

to simulate changes in the computing environment.

Then, using the *prmon*[5] tool, based on Unix's *proc*[7] different metrics were extracted with an update every ~12 ms:

- *wtime* - Wall Time;
- *utime* - Amount of time that this process has been scheduled in user mode, measured in CPU ticks;
- *stime* - Amount of time that this process has been scheduled in kernel mode, measured in CPU ticks;
- *nthreads* - Number of threads used;
- *rss* - Resident Share Size, i.e. the total amount of memory actually held in RAM for a process;
- *pss* - Proportional Share Size, i.e the amount of memory actually held in RAM for a process, accounting for libraries shared among multiples processes;
- *swap* - Amount of swap memory on disk;
- *vmem* - VM guest memory usage;

- *rchar* - The number of bytes which this task has caused to be read from storage;
- *read_bytes* - Attempt to count the number of bytes which the process really did cause to be fetched from the storage layer;
- *wchar* - The number of bytes which this task has caused, or shall cause to be written to disk;
- *write_bytes* - Attempt to count the number of bytes which this process caused to be sent to the storage layer;
- *rx_bytes* - Received bytes through network;
- *rx_packets* - Received packets through network;
- *tx_bytes* - Transmitted bytes through network;
- *tx_packets* - Transmitted packets through network.

2.1 Data Cleansing and Visualization

The first step was to visualize the data to have a glimpse of the problem and then proceed with the parametrization of the time series.

One of the plots is presented below.

Although it was not the goal of this work, through the initial plotting of the data some inconsistencies were found leading to the discovery of bugs in the data acquisition process which were then promptly corrected.

3 Single Dimensional Case

The first goal of the project was, given a univariate signal describing the usage of a specific resource by a given job with given settings and restrictions, to try and parametrize it in a simpler way.

A piecewise-linear function was chosen as the function to describe the signal, with parameters given by the different slopes, regressing on time, and by the timesteps at which the slope changes, i.e. the signal *change-points*.

While it was almost immediate to fit piecewise-linear functions to the signals by manually identifying its change-points, it was quite harder when that procedure was performed in an automatic way which was imperative given the high number of signals.

Moreover, even the *number* of change-points in a given signal was unknown, as different signals showed different up or down spike patterns.

Figure 1: CMS *gensim* job resource usage under different bandwidth restrictions

3.1 Problem Statement

Formally, given a time series of n timesteps, we want to identify m changepoints $\tau = (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_m)$, with unknown m , that minimize the function:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{m+1} [\mathcal{C}(y_{(\tau_{i-1}+1):\tau_i})] + \beta f(m) \quad (1)$$

Defining $\tau_0 = 0, \tau_{m+1} = n$ and y as the response variable. \mathcal{C} is a cost function on the segments and $\beta f(m)$ is a penalty to guard against overfitting and the creation of potentially n changepoints which would lead to a perfect, yet trivial, fit.

Different algorithms use different \mathcal{C} and f functions.

3.2 Tried Approaches

3.2.1 PELT

After reviewing the literature, the first implemented algorithm was the *PELT* (Pruned Exact Linear Time) algorithm, which uses binary segmentation, i.e. it applies the procedure outlined in formula 1, by first identifying a single changepoint in the time series and then by applying the same procedure in each of the resulting two segments and so on. The algorithm also implements pruning to speed up the process and let it achieve linear time computation, as its name suggests. [8]

The original implementation uses the negative maximum log-likelihood as \mathcal{C} and $f(m) = 1$. It is thus a parametric model, which was not readily applicable to the data at hand.

[6] extended the algorithm to the non-parametric case by using an *empirical* log-likelihood function based on [12] but its application led to an overdetection of changepoints, meaning that the penalty function f was not adequate for the data.

3.2.2 CPOP

The next tried algorithm was the *CPPOP* (Continuous-piecewise-linear Pruned Optimal Partitioning) outlined in [4] which minimizes the following variant of formula 1:

$$\min_{\tau} \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - f(i, \tau))^2 + \beta m \quad (2)$$

where $f(i, \tau)$ is the fitted value of a linear regression with dispersion parameter σ^2 at time i based on the inferred changepoint locations τ which determine changes in slope.

Formula 2 thus basically represents the MSE of a linear regression with the addition of an L_0 penalty.

The procedure also forces that the values at the end of a segment and the beginning of the following one be the same, enforcing *continuity* in this way.

To obtain the changepoints τ the algorithm implements a recursive procedure based on [8] for the changepoint location part and the same procedure as in [6] for the pruning part.

While the algorithm is indeed a parametric model, as it assumes a normal distribution for each segment while fitting the linear regressions, this assumption was deemed reasonable after observing the structure of the data. The only needed parameters were then σ^2 and β which were manually tuned. Eventually, the chosen values were $\sigma^2 = 1, \beta = 0.1$

3.2.3 FPOP

The FPOP (Functional Pruning Optimal Partitioning) [10] algorithm extends the CPOP algorithm by providing more pruning and therefore shorter computing times while at the same time not limiting it to the in-segment linear regression case and thus allowing more flexibility.

3.2.4 IDetect

The Isolate-Detect(IDetect) algorithm [2] is by far the most complicated among the tested ones and a thorough explanation of it is far beyond the scope and space allotted for this report. The interested reader can thus refer to the original paper.

It uses a radically different approach from the previous algorithms by employing a less *greedy* strategy while segmenting the series by first *globally* selecting segments which it estimates to contain one and only one changepoint and then optimizing *locally* the changepoint location in each of them, hence its name.

It is also one of the fastest experimented algorithms on the data at hand.

Unfortunately, it comes with a lot of hyperparameters, even though it is non-parametric by nature. These hyperparameters were also optimized manually for the analyzed data.

3.3 Uncertainty in the parametrization

In addition to the results produced by the different algorithms, it was considered important to produce an estimate of the uncertainty of the parametrizations.

The sample error of a linear regression on time fit within each segment was used as a proxy.

3.4 Results

The non-parametric version of the PELT algorithm led to an over-detection of change-points while its parametric version held very strong assumptions and was therefore not applicable to the data.

The CPOP algorithm was the one that gave the best results in terms of correspondence with the original series. A sample plot is shown below, with the shaded area representing the uncertainty of the predictions.

Figure 2: An example of CPOP results on one of the ATLAS tasks with restrictions on RAM

Unfortunately, the CPOP algorithm also came with long computational times. Therefore, the quicker FPOP and IDetect algorithms were tried as well to try and solve this problem.

While not reaching CPOP’s performance in terms of correspondence to the original, the IDetect algorithm led to acceptable results in a far shorter time, especially on longer series.

An example of the fit of the IDetect algorithm is shown below.

Figure 3: An example of IDetect results on one of the CMS tasks with restrictions on RAM

4 Multidimensional Case

The next step in the work would have been to try and extend the unidimensional case with the addition of the different restrictions. We would thus be able, *with a single model*, to have a glimpse of how the workloads change when different restrictions are applied.

Unfortunately, the previous phases proved to be harder than what was foreseen

and there was no time to investigate the multidimensional case.

5 Implementation

The presented procedures were implemented in the R programming language [11] as most literature on the subject had already been implemented in this language and lacked implementations in other popular languages such as Python.

The CPOP algorithm was implemented in R but was not packaged and instead only provided as raw source code. It was then packaged and documented in the final implementation of this work.

The IDetect algorithm had already been packaged by the original authors [1] and so their implementation was just adapted to the workloads' data by setting appropriate hyperparameters and creating a wrapper.

The two procedures together with a utility able to easily plot the data were packaged in the *NEREID* suite, which was uploaded and thoroughly documented on CERN's Gitlab and is made up of the R package *neReid* and various utility wrapper scripts.

6 Conclusions and future work

The work showcased various state-of-the-art changepoint detection algorithms and packaged them in a ready-to-use suite for the unidimensional case.

The multidimensional case still needs work. Eventually, the goal is to completely characterize a series, to then plug the output parameters into a data-center simulation model to estimate costs and benefit of a change to the architecture.

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